

Reproducible ML Workflows and Deployments with Tapis

Joe Stubbs¹, Nathan Freeman¹, Anagha Jamthe¹, Christian Garcia¹, Dhanny Indrakusuma¹

Texas Advanced Computing Center, Austin, TX, USA
{jstubbs, nfreeman, ajamthe, cgarcia}@tacc.utexas.edu, dhannywi@utexas.edu

Abstract:

This tutorial aims to provide researchers with a comprehensive introduction to the latest reproducible Machine Learning (ML) workflows and tooling provided by the NSF-funded Tapis v3 Application Programming Interface (API) and User Interface (UI). Through hands-on exercises, participants will gain experience in querying pre-trained ML models from public ML infrastructures such as Hugging Face or the ICICLE AI Institute, deploying various ML work-environments, and developing ML workflows on national-scale supercomputing resources. Throughout this tutorial, we will focus on utilizing the Tapis Workflows API, Tapis Pods API, Tapis ML Hub API, and TapisUI. These production-grade services are designed to simplify the facilitation and creation of trustworthy, reproducible, scientific workflows. By abstracting the complexities of underlying technologies behind user-friendly APIs, the Tapis services enable seamless integration with high performance computing (HPC) resources available at institutions with a Tapis deployment. Ultimately the tutorial aims to empower researchers to efficiently develop, deploy, and maintain their own ML workflows.

Description and Format:

We will set up training accounts for attendees so they can access Tapis resources regardless of their current TACC account creation status. Course material, including the slides and hands-on exercises for the tutorial, will be published on Github pages and will remain available to the attendees during and after the tutorial.

The section *Introduction to Tapis* will include theoretical concepts followed by simple hands-on-exercises. Attendees will be able to run the exercises in both Jupyter Notebooks and TapisUI. TapisUI is a serverless interactive science gateway that runs entirely on GitHub pages to interact with different Tapis services. A pre-computed example Jupyter notebook containing a description of building and running the scientific workflows will be available in case of internet outage. The tutorial will have a good mix of presentation and hands-on exercises for the attendees to learn and implement their own scientific computing workflows. We will have proctors working throughout the session to help attendees with the tutorial. The proposed tutorial schedule is as follows:

Time	Block	Topics
40 min	1	Introduction to Tapis, Authentication, TapisUI Overview
20 min	1	Introduction to Tapis Pods and deploy Pod instances
30 min	1	Introduction to Tapis ML Hub and interfacing with models
30 min	-	Break
25 min	2	Introduction to Tapis Workflows
20 min	2	Creating an ML workflow to facilitate automatic data collection
25 min	2	Overview of more Tapis use cases and integrations
10 min	2	Potential Tapis Use Cases (discussion with attendees)
10 min	2	Q/A

Tutorial Duration: 3 hours (excluding break)

Learning Outcomes:

By the end of this workshop attendees will be able to:

- Use Tapis APIs for creating and executing ML workflows
- Interact with Tapis ML Hub and interface with models
- Deploy instances with the Pods API which utilize GPU resources
- Launch ML oriented JupyterHub instances alongside other ML containers
- Understand how to create defined workflows for a real-world scientific use-case
- Have a basic understanding of deploying LLM models from Hugging Face
- Utilize Tapis UI to interact with Tapis services

Target Audience:

The audience for this workshop fits into three categories:

- 1) Researchers that utilize national, campus and local cyberinfrastructure resources and wish to do so in a reproducible, scalable and programmable manner.
- 2) Cyberinfrastructure specialists such as research software engineers (RSE), gateway providers/developers and infrastructure administrators. People in these roles can utilize open source technologies and state-of-the-art techniques to enable portable, reproducible computation.

3) Cyberinfrastructure directors, managers and facilitators that are looking for solutions to aid and educate their institutional researchers in order to better leverage local and distributed computational and cyberinfrastructure resources.

Content Level:

Beginner 70%, Intermediate 30%

Audience Prerequisites:

Attendees should have DockerHub accounts. Attendees must use their own laptop for the hands-on part of the tutorial. Attendees should have TACC accounts or use day-of training credentials.

Acknowledgement:

This workshop material is based upon work supported by the National Science Foundation Plant Cyberinfrastructure Program (DBI-0735191), the National Science Foundation Plant Genome Research Program (IOS-1237931 and IOS-1237931), the National Science Foundation Division of Biological Infrastructure (DBI-1262414), the National Science Foundation Division of Advanced Cyberinfrastructure (1127210), (2112606), and (1931439 and 1931575).

Presentation team:

Dr. Joe Stubbs is a Research Associate and leads the Cloud and Interactive Computing (CIC) group at the Texas Advanced Computing Center at the University of Texas at Austin. Dr. Stubbs is currently the PI of two NSF-funded projects and has played a fundamental role in developing numerous national-scale cyberinfrastructure systems for various scientific and engineering communities used by thousands of researchers.

Previous trainings:

- PEARC 23: Best Practices of CI/CD for High Performance Computation with Tapis Workflows API
- PEARC 22: Building Portable, Scalable and Reproducible Scientific Workloads across Cloud and HPC for Gateways
- TACCster 2022: Tapis day at TACC
- Gateways 21: Portable, Scalable, and Reproducible Scientific Computing: from Cloud to HPC
- PEARC 2020: Leveraging Tapis For Portable, Reproducible High Performance Computing In the Cloud
- Gateways 2019: Portable, Reproducible High Performance Computing In the Cloud

- PEARC 2019: Portable, Reproducible High Performance Computing In the Cloud

Nathan Freeman is an Engineering Scientist Associate in the Cloud and Interactive Computing (CIC) group at the Texas Advanced Computing Center at the University of Texas at Austin. Nathan manages the development of the Tapis Workflows API and related services, libraries, and UI.

Previous trainings:

- PEARC 23: Best Practices of CI/CD for High Performance Computation with Tapis Workflows API
- TACCster 2022: Tapis day at TACC

Dr. Anagha Jamthe is a Research Associate in the Cloud and Interactive Computing group (CIC) at the Texas Advanced Computing Center at the University of Texas at Austin. Dr. Jamthe has played a key role in developing and validating Tapis APIs.

Previous trainings:

- PEARC 23: Best Practices of CI/CD for High Performance Computation with Tapis Workflows API
- TACCster 2022: Tapis day at TACC
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- PEARC 2019: Portable, Reproducible High Performance Computing In the Cloud

Christian Garcia is an Engineering Associate in the Cloud and Interactive Computing group (CIC) at the Texas Advanced Computing Center at the University of Texas at Austin. Christian manages the Tapis Pods Service and related services, libraries, and UI.

Dhanny Indrakusuma is a Research Assistant in the Cloud and Interactive Computing group (CIC) at the Texas Advanced Computing Center at the University of Texas at Austin. Dhanny manages the Tapis ML Hub and related services, libraries and UI.

Resources:

- 1) Tapis Project: <https://tapis-project.org>
- 2) Tapis v3 documentation: <https://tapis.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>
- 3) Tapis Slack <http://bit.ly/join-tapis>